

May 1, 2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
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International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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AHOLINI IJTIMOIIY HIMOYA QILISH TIZIMIDA TIBBIY SUG'URTANI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI VA UNDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy ishda aholini ijtimoiy himoya qilish tizimida tibbiy sug'urtaning o'rnini va ahamiyati chuqur o'rganilib, rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan davlatlar tajribasi asosida ushbu tizimni samarali tashkil etishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari tahlil qilingan. Xususan, Germaniya, Fransiya, Janubiy Koreya va Turkiya kabi davlatlarning sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi tibbiy sug'urta modellarining tuzilmasi, moliyalashtirish manbalari, qamrov darajasi hamda fuqarolarga taqdim etiladigan xizmat sifati o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, ushbu tajribalar asosida O'zbekiston sharoitida ijtimoiy tibbiy sug'urta tizimini bosqichma-bosqich joriy etish, moliyaviy barqarorlikni ta'minlash, xizmatlar sifati oshirish va aholi qatlamlarini kengroq qamrab olish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonda sog'liqni saqlash tizimini modernizatsiya qilish va fuqarolarning ijtimoiy himoyasini kuchaytirishda tibbiy sug'urtaning salmoqli o'rnini borligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tibbiy sug'urta, sog'liqni saqlash tizimi, ijtimoiy himoya, sog'liqni saqlashni moliyalashtirish, xorij tajribasi, O'zbekiston, tibbiy xizmat sifati, islohotlar, sog'lom turmush, aholining salomatligi.

Aholining salomatligini ta'minlash – har qanday davlatning ijtimoiy siyosatidagi ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Sog'liqni saqlash tizimi samaradorligini ta'minlashda tibbiy sug'urta mexanizmlari muhim o'rin tutadi. Bugungi kunda O'zbekistonda sog'liqni saqlash tizimini modernizatsiya qilish, aholining barcha qatlamlari uchun sifatli tibbiy xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatini kengaytirish va moliyaviy yukni adolatli taqsimlash zarurati ortib bormoqda. Bu borada xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi, xususan rivojlangan mamlakatlarda qo'llanilayotgan majburiy va ixtiyoriy tibbiy sug'urta modellarini o'rganish katta ahamiyatga ega. Dunyo tajribasiga nazar tashlaydigan bo'lsak, tibbiy sug'urtaning samarali mexanizmlari Germaniya, Fransiya, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreya kabi davlatlarda shakllangan. Germaniyada "Bismarck modeli" asosida sog'liqni saqlash tizimi tashkil etilgan bo'lib, unda ish beruvchilar va ishchilar tomonidan to'lanadigan badallar orqali sug'urta fondlari shakllanadi. Bu tizimda barcha aholi qatlamlari qamrab olingan, xizmatlar sifatli va raqobatbardosh hisoblanadi.

Fransiyada esa davlat tomonidan ko'p darajali tibbiy sug'urta tizimi mavjud bo'lib, asosiy xarajatlarni davlat qoplaydi, qo'shimcha xarajatlar esa shaxsiy sug'urta kompaniyalari orqali qoplanadi. Yaponiya sog'liqni saqlash tizimi esa

butun aholiga birdek xizmat ko'rsatadigan, nisbatan markazlashgan modelga asoslangan bo'lib, unda ham ish beruvchilarning hissasi muhim o'rin tutadi. Janubiy Koreyada davlat va xususiy sektor ishtirokida tashkil etilgan majburiy tibbiy sug'urta tizimi natijasida aholining deyarli 100% sug'urta bilan qamrab olingan. Bu tizim sog'liqni saqlash xarajatlarini kamaytirish, tibbiy xizmatlar sifati va shaffofligini oshirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

O'zbekiston sog'liqni saqlash tizimida tibbiy sug'urta g'oyasi 2021-yildan boshlab faol muhokama qilina boshlandi. Ayni paytda ayrim hududlarda tajriba tariqasida majburiy tibbiy sug'urta tizimi joriy etilmoqda. Jumladan, Sirdaryo viloyatida amalga oshirilgan pilot loyiha aholining davlat tomonidan kafolatlangan bepul tibbiy xizmatlar paketiga ega bo'lishi imkonini berdi. Davlat tomonidan qamrab olinadigan aholi guruhlari aniqlangan, moliyalashtirish manbalari shakllantirilmoqda. Biroq hali bu tizim mamlakat miqyosida to'liq joriy qilinmagan. Qonunchilik, texnologik infratuzilma, raqamlashtirish, statistik monitoring va sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlari sifati bo'yicha hal qilinishi lozim bo'lgan bir qator muammolar mavjud.

Xulosa

Tibbiy sug'urta – aholining sog'lig'ini saqlashda ijtimoiy himoya mexanizmlarining eng muhim vositalaridan biridir. Jahon tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlarining sifatli, barqaror va adolatli bo'lishi ko'p jihatdan tibbiy sug'urta tizimining to'g'ri yo'lga qo'yilganiga bog'liq. Germaniya, Fransiya, Janubiy Koreya kabi davlatlar amaliyoti shuni tasdiqlaydiki, davlat va xususiy sektor o'rtasidagi optimal hamkorlik, aholining keng qatlamlarini qamrab olish, raqamli texnologiyalarning keng joriy etilishi tizim samaradorligini oshiradi. O'zbekistonda tibbiy sug'urtani joriy qilish yo'lida dastlabki qadamlar tashlangan bo'lsa-da, bu yo'nalishda hal qilinishi zarur bo'lgan ko'plab masalalar mavjud. Sug'urta tizimining bosqichma-bosqich joriy qilinishi, moliyaviy barqarorlikni ta'minlovchi mexanizmlarning ishlab chiqilishi, axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llash, kadrlar salohiyatini oshirish va aholining bu boradagi xabardorligini kuchaytirish orqali O'zbekiston sharoitida samarali tibbiy sug'urta tizimini yaratish mumkin. Bu esa sog'liqni saqlash sohasini yanada rivojlantirishga, aholining turmush sifati va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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